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Immunologically active factors produced during senescence.

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Cell-intrinsic and cell-extrinsic mechanisms regulate senescence resulting from natural sources like aging and oncogene expression and or artificial triggers like cell culture passage in vitro. We describe here a set of soluble immune factors whose expression is enriched in whole transcriptome measurement of cellular senescence. Cellular senescence was characterized by induction of specific soluble interferons including interferons L2, W1, and A16. Senescence program interferons functioned in concert with interleukins IL-9, IL-29, IL-20, and IL-21. Expression of senescence program interferons was associated with specific activation of interferon alpha isoforms IFNA21, IFNA2 and IFNA7, as well as interferon epsilon (IFNE). Co-regulation of cancer antigen CT62, pregnancy antigen PSG2, and testis-specific antigen TEX11 with senescence interferons indicated these soluble immune factors functioned in senescence activation in transformed cellular settings (cancer).